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“...[it] is called hot cement, because [it] is made and used with fire.”

A study of medieval stone adhesives through written sources, physical finds and experimental reconstruction

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a research project on medieval stone adhesives, combining historical source analysis, case studies and experimental reconstruction. Triggered by a multitude of finds at Stavanger Cathedral (Norway), the project investigates the broader technological scope of hot melt adhesive systems based on tar and resin, with additives like beeswax and brick dust.

Written sources and case studies alone risk to leave crucial knowledge gaps when researching performative craft procedures. To address this, the project integrates experimental craft science in the form of reconstructing adhesives to test hypotheses and reveal dimensions of tacit knowledge. This interdisciplinary approach works towards reconstruction as a method for understanding technical processes and material behaviour of adhesive application in historic stonemasonry.

Keywords: stone adhesives; craft knowledge; written sources; case studies; reconstruction

INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a research project, the aim of which is to study stone adhesive systems used in medieval stonemasonry. Central to this project is the role of experimental reconstruction, which plays a crucial part in achieving a comprehensive understanding of this craft technique. My research is organized into three distinct approaches, each covering a unique body of knowledge. The first approach consists of an extensive study of written sources, such as craft manuals and historic recipes. The second includes the observation, mapping and analysis of actual finds. And thirdly, the practical reconstruction of selected recipes in predefined conditions.

In my talk, I will briefly present the research project that has initiated a renewed focus on medieval stone adhesives. I will then provide an overview of different types of adhesives used in stonemasonry, supported by practical examples drawn from historical recipes and my own work experience in the field. Subsequently, I will present my research approach, emphasizing the critical role that experimental reconstruction plays in bridging the knowledge gap between written sources and physical finds.

POINT OF DEPARTURE

In 2023, circa 500 medieval stone repairs were detected in the masonry of the Gothic reconstruction phase (~1250) of Stavanger Cathedral in southwestern Norway. The carved stonework is made from local soapstone and the variety of bonds ranges from small indents and repairs to the assembly of whole blocks (see Figs. 01, 02). Initial analysis of the finds showed a multi-component mixture of pine tar as a main binder, beeswax as modifier and brick dust as a filler (Ebert & Bjelland, 2023).

These being the only published stone adhesive finds in Norway so far, the discovery in Stavanger initiated an international research project, led by the Museum of Archaeology (University of Stavanger) and funded by the Research Council of Norway (project number 344868; see project website: www.uis.no/en/museum-of-archaeology/research/sticking-stones-rediscovering-medieval-wood-tar-adhesives-for-stone). Its aim is to investigate the finds, compare them on a national and international level with material elsewhere, and subsequently reengineer an adhesive for use in modern day heritage conservation (Ebert, 2024).

Fig. 01: Stavanger Cathedral, detail of the stone carving; Anette Øvreid, Museum of Archaeology University of Stavanger

Fig. 02: Stavanger Cathedral, medieval repair of a stiff leaf; the adhesive bond (red arrow) is additionally secured by a lead pin (white arrow); Silas Ploner

HISTORIC STONE ADHESIVES

Historic stone adhesive systems, as defined in this paper, are hot melt adhesives (HMAs). They are multi-component systems, based on natural resins or tars as main binders, mixed with plasticizers such as beeswax and mineral fillers (Kilian Anheuser, 2001; Langejans et al., 2022). These mixtures need to be processed and applied hot on pre-heated surfaces, adding a significant technical challenge to their application. HMAs have frequently been spotted by masons, craftspeople or conservators of architectural heritage in various works of stonemasonry, but documented finds or analysis of historic adhesive samples are rare and isolated (Anheuser, 1999; Ribechini et al., 2009; Hoepner & Zollfrank, 2022; Ebert & Bjelland, 2023). Basic patterns of usage can be deduced from the observation of various artistic expressions of stonemasonry – from the art of *opus sectile* and *pietra dura* to historic sculpture restoration, to stone claddings (see Figs. 03, 04).

Only very few workshops operating today use similar adhesive systems. One of them is the restoration workshop of the *Prussian Palace Department* in Potsdam (Germany), focusing on small-scale works of *pietra dura* as well as stone floors and wall panels. Their experiential knowledge is an outstanding source, but only sparsely recorded or published (Klappenbach, 2013; Sommer & Klappenbach, 2013). The current state of research on historic stone adhesives is based mostly on observations, sporadic analysis of finds and isolated evaluation of artist manuals.

Fig. 03: Cross-sectional view of the construction of a Pietra Dura tabletop with supporting plate, adhesive bond and inlay work; Silas Ploner

Fig. 04: Brixen Cathedral; column clad with thin strips of cut stones; Silas Ploner

RESEARCH DESIGN and QUESTIONS

To work towards a more comprehensive understanding of this craft, my research builds on three complementary approaches.

It starts with a full reconstruction of all crucial work steps described in written sources. In this analysis, I include historic recipes as extracted from artist manuals as well as medieval invoices or entries in material compendia. But furthermore, historical texts depict a wide range of different recipes and material combinations. To what extent were these mixtures tailored to very specific individual applications? This body of written knowledge often faces epistemic limitations, especially when researching detailed technical descriptions. Detailed technical descriptions are often missing; weights and ratios are either non-existent or seem highly unlikely.

Case studies of selected buildings will provide phenomenological mapping and classification of use-cases together with material analysis of samples. The practical challenges to being selection of finds, accessibility and chance. Can material choices be traced back to regional traditions and the availability of materials? Or are there distinct and conscious application patterns to be uncovered, linking each system and each recipe to a specific climatic or structural challenge?

Both approaches – the study of written tradition and physical remains - are firmly rooted in the fields of historical source study and building archaeology.

Between these two juxtapositions, several research questions can be derived from the material itself, focusing on the relation between material choices and practical application methods.

The specific technical challenges of HMAs can be illustrated by a simplified dynamic relationship between three key factors: *heat*, *viscosity*, and *material properties*.

Understanding and using these thermos-physical properties plays a crucial in the performance of hot-melt adhesives. To specifically approach these performative procedures, experimental craft science was integrated into the research design as a third approach.

Exemplary research questions arising from the observation of sources and finds are: Which material combinations and temperatures were required to form specific bond surfaces and orientations? How was head achieved and transferred? And how did material modifications alter the system of heat, viscosity and application properties?

RECONSTRUCTION AS METHODOLOGY

Experimental craft research will not just serve as an addition, but as a source of knowledge production itself, linking the outcomes of all three studies and putting hypotheses and findings to the test. Starting with a practical presentation from one of the workshops still using historic adhesives today, I show how practical reconstruction can serve as an essential step in the understanding of operational procedures (see Fig. 05, 06). The craftspeople are recognised as valid sources of experiential knowledge. As personal experience meets the specific observations and unique materials from Stavanger Cathedral, new questions, ideas and possible solutions take shape.

Fig. 05: Raw materials for a basic historic hot-melt adhesive: beeswax and colophony (rosin); Silas Ploner

Fig. 06: The cooked mixture is cooled on a wet metal plate and rolled into convenient sticks; Silas Ploner

Taking the material itself as a transmitter of knowledge challenges the tendency to interpret historical substances through the lens of modern expectations and technical standards, not only aiming to measure final material properties, but examining the sensory decisions necessary to select various ingredients and their influences. The experiential element of feeling, sensing and perceiving is validated as an essential measuring rod (O'Neill & O'Sullivan, 2019).

My paper shows how the material encounter of reconstruction is crucial in closing knowledge gaps that are neither covered by written sources nor deducible through observation or analysis.

CONCLUSION

This paper advocates for the deliberate integration of three different methodological approaches - not lining them up in a sequential manner but allowing them to influence each other simultaneously. Practical reconstruction and craft science become an integral part of a multi-faceted strategy. The study of written sources as well as the results of analysis serve as a foundation for material choices as well as provider for further hypotheses. In this manner, historical research and experimental reconstruction can influence one another on multiple levels.

This holistic framework can help to shed detailed and comprehensive light on a forgotten craft technique that still waits to be recognised for its immense technical complexity and achievement.

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